

D4.1. Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan

M15 updated version (V2)

Deliverable Information Sheet

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1. Executive Summary

The deliverable D4.1 *Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan (D&C&E Plan)* describes the strategy underlying all promotional, informative, and outreaching activities that will be performed over the course of the project.

It also serves as a roadmap for the management and monitoring of the dissemination activities, with a focus on reaching the greatest possible outreach of the project's activities and results to the targeted stakeholder groups, as well as to effectively and fully draw on the stakeholder engagement for the updating of the project's activities and actions.

Specifically, the deliverable identifies and prioritises target stakeholders, such as fertiliser producer and users, and key messages to deliver, describes dissemination measures for results as well as communication tools and strategic channels to be used, exploitation measures, key performance indicators – KPIs – for all project's D&E&C measures and EU funding obligations. In addition, as mentioned above, the deliverable sets up procedures for monitoring communication activities carried out by all project partners throughout the project with the purpose to assess communication impacts.

The deliverable is conceived as a living document to be updated as the project progresses. This present version represents the first update after 15 months of project implementation. All the updates and adjustments will be reported in the deliverable D4.3 *FER-PLAY post-project D&C&E and sustainability Plan*, which is intended to give evidence of the communications effort and the impact of the planned activities.

As leader of Work Package 4 (Dissemination exploitation and communication), the European Biogas Association will be responsible for the overall monitoring of the communications activities. Nevertheless, all project partners will contribute to disseminate and communicate about the project within their networks and will provide their feedback to ensure the impact assessment of the communication and dissemination activities.

2. Project overview

The overall aims of the FER-PLAY (Multi-assessment of alternative fertilisers for promoting local sustainable value chains and clean ecosystems) project are:

- to map and assess the potential and impacts of alternative fertilisers from secondary raw materials,
- to increase awareness about their multiple benefits,
- and to promote the wide-scale production and application of the ones with the best environmental, social, economic and technical performance.

Figure 1. FER-PLAY Work packages

Implementation of FER-PLAY follows a logical order of four steps.

2.1. Step 1 – Alternative fertiliser value chains mapping and selection

In the first step, currently available but scattered data and knowledge on alternative fertilisers value chains will be collected and harmonised by applying a funnelling process based on the developed

GO/NO-GO approach. Afterwards, a scoring system will be used to select the most promising value chains following a set of defined scoring criteria.

2.2. Step 2 – Impact assessment of selected value chains

The data on the selected value chains will be complemented via assessment (at global/ EU/ local scale) of their environmental, social, economic impacts & trade-offs (via LCSA) as well as their technical and regulatory aspects.

This step includes (i) harmonising the results of the existing studies and (ii) conducting complementary assessments.

2.3. Step 3 – Co-creation processes

Horizontally, spaces for dialogue and participation will be created with key stakeholders in the value chains with the aim to involve their perspectives in Step 2 as well as co- develop input for Step 4 (guidelines and recommendations targeted at the key stakeholders).

2.4. Step 4 – Awareness raising and public policies orientation

The project results will be disseminated among key stakeholders through relevant actions. The present document is aimed at describing dissemination, communication and exploitation tasks in more details.

Figure 2. FER-PLAY methodology overview

3. Target audiences and key messages

FER-PLAY dissemination and communication activities will be shaped according to the needs of the different target groups, and consistently to their immediate or more long-term strategic importance for the project. This will allow us to determine and schedule the most appropriate communications activities to be used, as well as messages to be delivered.

There are six target audiences that have been identified by the FER-PLAY consortium:

1. **Farmers (individual, cooperatives, unions, etc.)** contributing to the supply (e.g. residues and demand (e.g. compost) of fertilisers. The goal of engaging with them is to improve their awareness of existence and performance of alternative fertilisers, reduce their negative connotations about recycled nutrients and eliminate scepticism towards their use.

Key messages to be delivered:

- Benefits of the use of alternative fertilisers and how to apply them to restore soil fertility.
- Which fertiliser to choose per crop type.

2. **Conventional and alternative fertiliser producers:** the goal is to increase their knowledge about nutrient recovery technologies available and benefits of the use of recovered nutrients in fertilisers.

Key messages to be delivered:

- Which value chains have lower impact, better performance, etc.
- How alternative fertilisers could create new business cases.

3. **Public administrations,** especially those related to waste stream management, agricultural planning and resource management. The goal is to increase their knowledge about the value chains and provision of objective data to support decision-making and policy formulation. They will be also provided with tools to map and characterize secondary resources.

Key messages to be delivered:

- Actions should be taken on a policy-level to allow the use and to boost the demand and uptake of alternative fertilisers.

- How to contribute to the achievement of international and EU agreements and future EU policies on soil health.

4. **Academia and research**, with the focus on universities and RTOs that work with circular economy, agro-environment). The goal is to increase their knowledge about promising value chains for future research and to communicate about reliable methodologies for mapping and impact assessment.

Key messages to be delivered:

- What technologies/methods perform better to recover nutrients.
- What methodologies could be used for value chain assessment.

5. **Other industry that could benefit from the project outcomes:** the goal is to present to this audience potential secondary uses of waste streams and ways to comply with nutrients' content limits in the discharges.

Key message to be delivered:

- Benefit of nutrient recovery to their business.
- Identification of technologies and fertiliser products that perform better and could be implemented.

6. **Consortia of other relevant EU projects:** the goal is to create synergies and communicate methodologies and results.

Key message to be delivered:

- How to contribute to a holistic approach for zero pollution and future EU soil policy
- How to synchronize data collection

4. Dissemination activities

The dissemination measures aim to spread the knowledge generated in the project to target audiences at dedicated events across Europe as well as through knowledge products and articles in scientific journals and specialized media. Figure 3. provides an overview of the project resources and measures for their dissemination towards the target groups.

Figure 3. Dissemination overview

4.1. Guidelines and recommendations

As shown in the Figure 3. above, Step 3 of the project concerns the co-development of the resources presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1. FER-PLAY guidelines and recommendations

Name	Description	Month	Responsible partner
Guidelines for the fertiliser end users (D3.1)	Compilation of key non-technical, technical, market and regulatory information related to the application of alternative fertilisers, tailored to the crop type.	M25	NATURLAND

Guidelines for the fertiliser producers (D3.2)	Compilation of key non-technical, technical, market and regulatory information related to the manufacture of alternative fertilisers.	M25	CIC
Recommendations for public administrations (D3.3)	Practical suggestions in the form of policy briefs to help policy makers to deliver successful strategies and instruments for the market deployment of alternative fertilisers.	M25	ACR+
Exploitation strategies (D.4.3)	Guidelines that will allow the broader market exploitation of the selected commercial fertilisers and for the establishment of the road to market for the new fertilisers	M30	DRAXIS

4.2. Dissemination events

The goal of the dissemination events is to share the guidelines and recommendations described in Section 4.1 (or partial results if an event takes place before their publication) directly with the target audiences and to interact with them.

The events will be organised by relevant project partners, in cooperation with the EBA.

The table 2. lists all planned activities from the beginning of the project:

Table 2. Dissemination activities

Month	Activity	Responsible partner
M7	Seminar for farmers and technicians	INAGRO
M10	2 Network meetings with fertilisers producers	(1 EBA, 1 CIC)
M14	2 Workshops for organic and young farmers	(1 NATURLAND, 1 ASAJA)
M20	Workshop for other EU project coordinators	CETENMA
M25	Seminar for farmers and technicians	INAGRO
M28	Workshop for local and regional authorities	ACR+
M28	Policy webinar	EBA

M28	2 Workshops for organic and young farmers	(1 NATURLAND, 1 ASAJA)
M29	Workshop for decision makers from EU regions	ACR+
M30	2 Network webinars with fertilisers producers	(1 EBA, 1 CIC)
M13 and 25	Open days/field demonstrations	NuReSys & INAGRO
TBC	Webinar for COPA-COGECA members	COLDIRETTI

4.3. Presence at external events

The next Table presents possible events that FER-PLAY consortium can attend:

Table 3. List of relevant external events

Date	Activity	Country	Target group	Responsible partner
June '23	Öko-Feldtage (Organic Field Days)	Germany	Farmers, public administration, academia	NATURLAND
Autumn '23	ESNI (European Sustainable Nutrient Initiative) conference	Belgium	Academia, Fertiliser producers	EBA
Sept '23	Sanatech Exhibition	Italy	Farmers	CIC
Oct '23 & '24	European Biogas Conference	Belgium	Producers, academia, other industries, public administration	EBA
Nov '23	Ecomondo Fair	Italy	Producers, other industries	CIC
Jan '24	SOFIE ₃ conference	Belgium	Academia, producers	EBA
Feb '24	Fieragricola Fair	Italy	Farmers, producers	CIC
2024	Expo Biogaz Fair	France	Producers, other industries	EBA
March '24	ManuREsource Conference	Belgium	Academia	INAGRO, EBA
April '24	NERM 2024 (Nutrients in Europe Research Meeting)	Belgium	Academia	CETENMA
May '24	SETAC Europe 34th Annual Meeting	Spain	Academia	CETAQUA
May '24	IFAT Fair	Germany	Producers, other industries	CIC
June '24	EUBCE Conference and Fair	France	Academia, producers, other industries	EBA
Sept '24	LCA Food Conference	Spain	Academia, other industries	CETAQUA
Sept '24	SDEWES Conference	Italy	Academia	CETAQUA

4.4. Final event

Towards the end of the project (M30), a final event will be organized in Brussels to present the main results and recommendations of the project. The event is intended to gather the representatives of target groups presented in Section 3. The estimated number of participants is 100. The event will be promoted on the project website, newsletter, and social media channels, as well as all FER-PLAY partners. Two press releases will be issued, before and after the event, to increase participation in the event and the dissemination of its results.

4.5. Collaboration with other projects and networks

As mentioned in Table 3., there is the plan to organise a workshop by M20 in Brussels to generate synergies and strengthen relations with representatives from projects funded under the present topic and from other EU projects (e.g. Fertimanure, Nutriman).

FER-PLAY consortium has also established closer cooperation with the 'sister' project NOVAFERT (Novel procedures and sustainable guidelines to enhance the use of alternative fertilisers, Grant Agreement N° 101060835) that was approved under the same call for action HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-09 'Environmental impacts and trade-offs of alternative fertilizing products at global/local scale'.

FER-PLAY & Novafert

Figure 4. Potential synergies between FER-PLAY and NOVAFERT

The project cluster organized the joint kick-off meeting in the presence of the European Commission on 9 November 2022, during which similarities and potential synergies were discussed, as shown in Figure 4. Following areas for joint actions were identified:

- Mapping of value chains and mapping innovative nutrient oriented living labs
 - Data collection
 - Lighthouse demos
- Environmental assessment
 - Data collection
 - Methodology development and discussion
- Exploitation strategies
 - Action plans
 - Co-creation of guidelines
- Awareness and dissemination
 - Potential joint dissemination actions: awareness campaigns, events, conferences (ESNI, ManuResource) workshops (especially in Belgium and Spain), etc.
- Policy making
 - Identification of joint policy briefings with inputs from both projects
 - Regulatory framework analysis and joint recommendations list
- Advisory board

- The coordinator of each project is a member of the other project's advisory board

Further details of this collaboration were provided in the report on the first outcomes of clustering with sister projects (D2.4., M12).

In addition, the FER-PLAY consortium joined the Biorefine Cluster Europe (BCE), managed by Ghent University (NOVAFERT coordinator). BCE gathers projects within the domain of biobased resource recovery. The cluster facilitates sharing knowledge, organizing joint activities and communicating about the partner projects. Within the BCE, FER-PLAY joined the Nutrient Recycling Community, which gathers projects dedicated specifically, as the name suggests, to the nutrient recycling.

BCE also organizes annual European Sustainable Nutrient Initiative conference, where partner projects can present their work. FER-PLAY consortium has participated and will continue exploring the opportunities to participate in these events.

4.6. Articles and knowledge products

4.6.1. Scientific articles

To reach the research community, four articles in total will be published by CETAQUA and CETENMA in open-access scientific peer-reviewed journals, such as International Journal of Circular Economy, Waste Management, the Circular Economy and Sustainability Journal, and other journals assessing sustainable performance/impact. These publications will create knowledge impact and will enable other researchers to use the project's results in their own work, thus contributing to further dissemination of the project.

4.6.2. Informative articles

The consortium will publish four articles in specialized media, such as Agribusiness, Food Policy, Fertilisers Magazine, to reach the agri-business and environmental sectors. The articles will raise awareness about the project, the challenge it addresses, and the benefits of the proposed alternative fertiliser value chains. Figure 5. Shows an example of an article presenting the project:

OSSERVATORIO CIC

Cocreazione di condizioni per l'uso di fertilizzanti alternativi

Tutti insieme appassionatamente

Testo di **di Ambrogio Pigoli, Eva Lopez, Alberto Confalonieri**, Consorzio Italiano Compostatori

Il Consorzio Italiano Compostatori svolge un ruolo di primo piano nel Progetto Fer-Play, che vedrà la collaborazione di un nutrito gruppo di organizzazioni e centri di ricerca europei allo scopo di facilitare l'immissione sul mercato e l'impiego di fertilizzanti alternativi a quelli di sintesi

Lo scorso 21 settembre si è tenuto a Cartagena, in Spagna, il *kick off meeting* (la riunione di inizio dell'attività, per i non addetti ai lavori) di un progetto Horizon Europe denominato Fer-Play. Coordinato dal centro di ricerca spagnolo Centenna, il progetto europeo metterà al lavoro un corposo partenariato costituito per lo più da rappresentanti di organizzazioni e centri di ricerca prove-

Figure 5. Example of an article presenting the project, published in the Italian specialized magazine Acqua ed energia, (issue 6/2022)

5. Communication tools and activities

The key purpose of the FER-PLAY communication activities are to communicate about the project scope, objectives, results and impacts effectively to the target audiences outline in [Section 3](#) and the general public with the ultimate goal of raising awareness about the benefits of alternative fertilisers and fostering their production and usage. REVOLVE is the project partner responsible for the communication tasks.

The following channels and tools will be used and developed during the project:

- Project branding, including main messaging, visual identity and a logo and templates, for internal use;
- Communications Pack, including posters, e-banners, roll-ups, leaflets for external use;
- Project website, updated regularly;
- Newsletter and press releases;
- Social media channels;
- Videos and infographics.

5.1. Project branding

5.1.1. Project visual identity

The FER-PLAY visual identity plays an essential role in promoting the project, and includes a logo, tagline and colour palette to be reflected in communication materials. The detailed visual identity concept, usage guidelines, including the complete colour palette and alternative versions of the logo, can be seen in Annex 2., and are made available to partners to ensure the consistent representation of the project.

5.1.2. Project logo

The FER-PLAY logo (Figure 6.) includes three main elements:

1. Soil patch: highlighting the centrality of soil for the project, and the importance of soil health and quality for plant growth
2. Wheat stalk: representing agriculture and the agricultural sector as end-users
3. Play button: referring to change and action.

Figure 6. FER-PLAY main logo

In addition to the main logo, colour variations have been developed for use in various situations (Figure 7.):

Figure 7. FER-Play logo variations

5.1.3. Project main messaging

To ensure a consistent communication effort, a project description, a "Golden Paragraph" has been developed to be used to describe the project:

FER-PLAY is facilitating the uptake of alternative fertilisers, to protect ecosystems, decrease EU dependence on fertiliser imports, foster circularity and improve soil health. The project will map and assess alternative fertilisers made from secondary raw materials, such as manure or wastewater, and highlight their multiple benefits in order to promote their wide-scale production and use on field.

The project slogan or tagline is the lead message and should convey the essence of the mood being advanced by the project communication.

Alternative fertilisers for circularity & ecosystem health
 Circular fertilisers for sustainable agriculture & healthy soils/ecosystems
 Sustainable fertilisers for European autonomy & soil improvement

Sub-messaging for specific target audiences and communication materials will be developed on an ongoing basis, following the key messages outlined in [Section 3](#).

5.1.4. Document templates

Within FER-PLAY following templates have been designed and are available for partners' use on the project's Sharepoint:

- Deliverable template
- Report template
- PowerPoint presentation template
- Press Release template
- Newsletter template

In line with the visual identity and featuring the funding and content disclaimers as outline in [Section 8.2](#) all templates have a predetermined layout that must be respected by the FER-PLAY consortium.

5.2. Communication Channels

5.2.1. Project website

The FER-PLAY website is already functional under the address <https://fer-play.eu/>, and will be online for 4 years following the project's conclusion, to support the actions to be defined under D4.3 (D&E&C post-project sustainability plan).

The website will serve as the main channel for communication about the project and its activities and serve as a repository for project outputs and materials including deliverables, open-access scientific publications, informative articles, as well as relevant news and events from the project and related projects. The website also includes a sign-up form to the project's newsletter.

Figure 8. FER-PLAY website

5.2.2. Newsletter

A total of 5 newsletters will be released, starting in M7 (March 2023) and ending in M30 (January 2025), and will include information on project progress and results, links to public deliverables, articles, and upcoming events, using a custom template with the project's visual identity. They will be sent out through MailChimp and a public opt-in form that is GDPR compliant is available on project website.

The aims of the newsletters are:

- Informing project partners and stakeholders of the key findings of the project,
- providing information about relevant external events and publications, and
- disseminating key messages from Work Package Leaders.

5.2.3. Press Releases

The media are important to reaching both the general public and targeted audiences through specialised media. Three press releases will be produced during the lifetime of the project. The first was published in September following the Kick Off Meeting in Cartagena (Figure 9.). The second and third press releases will be developed in parallel with the organisation of the final event in M30. Press releases will be developed by REVOLVE and shared partners before publication. Partners will be requested to use their extensive networks to share widely and increase attendance to the final event and the dissemination of the projects final results and outputs.

[View this email in your browser](#)

NOVEMBER 2022

FER-PLAY: Promoting the use of alternative fertilisers

To reduce the environmental impact of European agriculture, decrease import dependence and foster the development of the circular economy, the recently launched FER-PLAY project is promoting the use of alternative fertilisers made from secondary resources. Over the course of the project, the FER-PLAY consortium will assess impacts and best practices for alternative fertilisers and increase awareness about their presence on market and their multiple benefits, to facilitate their uptake amongst key stakeholders.

[Read the press release](#)

Figure 9. Example of sharing a press release by a FER-PLAY partner

5.2.4. Social media channels

Twitter and LinkedIn profiles have been chosen to promote project-related contents to different audiences and take advantage of existing partner networks, thus building on their audience to communicate about the project and disseminate its results. A presence on relevant channels allows partners to contribute to the dissemination of results and events by tagging the project and highlighting their work, thus providing visibility to the project through their respective networks. The social media channels are key in building a community around the project and engaging with interested stakeholders. The selected platforms both offer a certain amount of analytics which will be consulted as part of the impact reporting process.

Twitter (Figure 10.): To target policy, media, and the general public.

Handle: @FER_PLAY_eu

Hashtag: #FERPLAYEU

Figure 10. Twitter account

LinkedIn (Figure 11.): To target industry, research, and media.

Company Page: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/fer-play-eu/about/>

Figure 11. LinkedIn page

5.3. Communication Materials

To support partners in their activities, communication materials and guidelines have been developed for use in external activities and events, to maintain a consistent presentation of the project. Materials are available for partners to use on [SharePoint](#) and have been gathered on a [Trello](#) board for partners to access easily for their communication and dissemination activities. The Trello board will be updated regularly to include new materials in English and other partner languages.

5.3.1. Leaflet

A project leaflet has been developed to share at events and includes a QR code linking to the website. The flyer provides information about FER-PLAY's step-by-step process, expected impacts, and partners.

5.3.2. Roll-ups and poster

A roll-up and a poster have been developed for use at events and includes a QR code linking to the website, which will be monitored. Both provide information about FER-PLAY's step-by-step process, expected impacts, and partners.

5.3.3. Videos

A total of six videos will be produced during the lifetime of the project and hosted on the project's YouTube playlist. To date, an introductory video about the project has been produced and can be viewed [here](#).

The tentative timeline and topics for the five remaining videos can be seen in the table below. The videos build on one another, presenting first an explanation of what fertilisers are, how FER-PLAY will foster their use and uptake, and running through the benefits for different stakeholder groups. The content will draw from ongoing work and deliverables from other work packages, including workshops and seminars outlined in Section 4.2.

Table 4. Tentative topics and timeline for video production

Video #	Tentative topic	Year
#2	What are alternative fertilisers?	Year 1
#3	Concept videographic explaining project's added value	Year 2
#4	Overview of 7 selected value chains (using D1.2, due in M8)	Year 2
#5	Why use alternative fertilisers? Targeting end-users and linking to D3.1, due M25 and outcomes from workshops and seminars (see Table 1)	Year 3
#6	Why produce alternative fertilisers / Novel products for a novel sector. Targeting fertiliser producers and linking to D3.2 due M25 and outcomes from workshops and seminars (see Table 1)	Year 3

5.3.4. Infographics

The project will produce a total of four infographics to support communication activities and be used in various communication materials.

A project methodology/concept infographic has already been developed and can be seen below in Figure 12.:

Figure 12. Project methodology/concept infographic

Three infographics will be developed in consultation with partners between M6 and M30 covering the main alternative fertiliser value chains by waste stream (Urban and industrial wastewater; biowaste; biological by-products, treated manure) – basing on visual presented in Figure 13., and highlighting the benefits of using alternative fertilisers. The content of the latter will be defined depending on the target audience for the infographic, drawing from D3.1 and D3.2 (both M25).

Figure 13. Main alternative fertiliser value chains from secondary raw materials (dark blue) and output products (light green)

5.3.5. Social media assets

E-banners for social media platforms (see Figure 9. and 10. above) and customised shareables using the project visual identity have been produced for use of social media platforms. Additional materials will be created on an ongoing basis according to communication needs. An example of social media visual is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Social media call to action to join the FER-PLAY newsletter

6. Exploitation Plan

Exploitation is one of the key factors of a project, since it contributes to the achievement of the expected impacts of the project, over time. Exploitation is differentiated from dissemination as, according to the IPR Helpdesk (European Commission, 2022), the latter refers to the public disclosure of the results by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the project outputs.

On the other hand, 'Exploitation' refers to research and innovation activities (R&I), different from the ones that generated the results, with the objective of effectively using these results through exploitation pathways (scientific, economic, political, societal, etc.) aiming to transform these actions into outcomes with value and impact for the society. Exploitation outcomes could lead to new policy recommendations, help mitigate a specific problem, have impact on the economic, societal and innovation environment among others.

Exploitation is a key factor of a project since it contributes to reach the expected impacts of the project over time, beyond the duration of a project. The process begins with the identification and generation of the project results, to their dissemination and exploitation and ultimately to the wider scientific, economic and societal impacts of the project destination (European Commission, 2021).

The Exploitation Plan, as part of the D&E&C plan, aims at identifying exploitable results in collaboration with project partners and assisting them in exploring potential pathways for impact creation, through exploitation, after the end of the project.

The Exploitation Plan differs from the Exploitation Strategies - Deliverable 4.2, to be developed within T4.3 - as it is aimed at identifying exploitable results for the project partners, while Deliverable 4.2 concerns exploitation strategies for the selected new and existing alternative fertilisers.

6.1. Methodology

This section presents the overall methodology, the general approach, the tools and methods that will be put in action for the collection of input from project partners and their respective results and to assist them to explore potential exploitation pathways after the end of the project.

The methodology is elaborated in two phases. The first one takes place during the first fifteen months of the project, and the second one continues until the end of the project. In specific, the aim of the first phase is that the partners identify the issues that need to be further addressed in the course of the project (e.g. characterization of exploitable results, Intellectual Property ownership of results, existence of

relevant markets, barriers for exploitation, etc.). On the other hand, the aim of the second phase is to detail by the end of the project a well-grounded plan on the partners' final intentions for exploitation of the project results. Considering that by the end of the first phase, the project would still run at its middle stages, it is not expected that the partners will have a clear view of all issues, so it is logical that during the second phase an update of all initial statements will also take place. The first phase concludes with the Exploitation plan presented in this document, while the second phase will be included in the final Exploitation plan (M30).

With respect to the plan for the exploitation of the project results, the overall methodology that was followed is mainly based on the publication of the EU IPR Helpdesk "Making the most of your H2020 project: boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation" (Haardt *et al.*, 2019). In brief, the methodology for the exploitation plan is built on the following steps:

1. Identification and characterization of project exploitable results
2. Review of Intellectual Property issues
3. Identification and selection of appropriate exploitation routes
4. Description of necessary activities for achieving exploitation.

The first step «Identification and characterization of project exploitable results» focuses on the elaboration, identification and mapping of the exploitable results, identified in the Grant Agreement of the project. During this first step, additional information has been collected regarding some key characteristics of the results such as the value proposition, innovation, significance, use and any alternative uses that the results could have. For the collection of all the needed information, partners were asked to answer a dedicated questionnaire, developed by Draxis, that was distributed on the 25th of May 2023. In addition, a workshop was held, on the same day, to familiarize the consortium members with the steps that they need to take, so as, in the one hand, reply to the questions and on the second hand help them better understand and design their results towards exploitation. In this way, the dedicated questionnaire would assist in the monitoring of partner's results, by collecting crucial information for each result and project partner. The questionnaire is thoroughly presented in Annex 4 – Exploitation questionnaire.

In addition, some market-oriented information has been investigated such as target groups, requirements, etc. The collected information has been used to construct the first updated version of the Exploitation Plan as provided in this report.

The second step «Review of Intellectual Property issues» investigates Intellectual Property (IP) issues. For this step, information was collected from the deliverables of WP5, specifically D5.1 Data management plan since they stress the issue of IP management for all the potential results. In this step,

issues such as the background and foreground IP related to the identified exploitable results are being investigated.

The third step «Identification and selection of appropriate exploitation routes» identifies routes for the exploitable results. Firstly, there needs to be a distinction between commercial and non-commercial exploitation of the results, commercial referring to those results that offer monetary gain to the partner(s) that has generated them and non-commercial being the ones not monetized by the relevant consortium member(s) (i.e. for political, societal and scientific purposes). Then, partners were informed regarding the available exploitation channels and investigated which suited them more. To maximize the project's impact, all relevant project partners will be split into groups and Exploitation meetings will be organized, towards the later stages of the project. The aim of those meetings will be to support and guide the consortium members in choosing the most effective exploitation channel for their result.

The fourth and final step "Description of necessary activities for achieving exploitation" is expected to take place during the later stages of the project, when the activities for ensuring the continuation of the exploitation of FER-PLAY's results after the project's end will be constructed. In that stage, the main customers/end users of the exploitable results, along with the key messages towards them will be clearly depicted, and whether the project results could meet the needs and requirements of them will be assessed. Furthermore, the existing competitors on the market, relevant to the project's exploitable outputs will be mapped.

The first two steps were completed during the first half of FER-PLAY, while the third and fourth step take place during the second half of the project (M15-M30).

6.2. Input Declared by Partners

This section presents the input declared by each partner regarding their identified exploitable result(s). As presented in Section 6.1, a questionnaire has been developed by Draxis and was presented on the 25th of May 2023 to all consortium members to familiarize themselves with the questionnaire.

The Table below presents each exploitable result by partner, type of result, assets, the current position in the market, project results and the expected outcome. These results, as stated before, will be enhanced by additional information during the lifetime of the project.

Table 5. Exploitable assets of the FER-PLAY project partners

Partner (Type)	Exploitable result (Type)	Main features	Exploitation type	Ownership status
CETENMA (RTO)	Alternative Fertilisers Database (Database)	Data on 60 alternative fertiliser value chains.	Non-commercial	Joint (CETENMA, INAGRO, CIC, EBA, NURESYS, CETAQUA, ACR+, COLDIRETTI, NATURLAND, ASAJA)
	Environmental LCA (Consulting Services)	Evaluation of 7 circular fertiliser value chains based on their environmental impacts.	Commercial	Joint (Fer-Play Consortium)
	Social LCA (Consulting Services)	Evaluation of 7 value chains, bearing in mind different stakeholders like society, local community and workers.	Commercial	Joint (Fer-Play Consortium)
	Economic LCA (Guidelines and Recommendations)	Evaluation of 7 value chains, analyzing acquisition, operation, maintenance and disposal costs.	Commercial	Joint (Fer-Play Consortium)
	Sustainability LCA (Consulting Services)	Evaluation of the three pillars of sustainability: economics, environment, and society.	Commercial	Joint (Fer-Play Consortium)
CIC (NPO)	Practical handbook for circular fertilisers use (Guidelines and Recommendations)	Description of the different circular fertilisers, their characteristics and application modality and machinery required for their uses.	Non-commercial	Joint (CIC, NATURLAND, ASAJA, COLDIRETTI, INAGRO & CETENMA)
	Practical handbook for circular fertilisers production (Guidelines and Recommendations)	Guidelines focusing on commercial and regulatory drivers to permit obtainment and for raising awareness of end-users, instruments for the improvement of cost-benefit ratio, and how to gain acceptance of the production facility in the territory.	Non-commercial	Joint (CIC, EBA, NURESYS, COLDIRETTI & CETENMA)
	Recommendations for public administrations (Guidelines and Recommendations)	Policy briefs, with practical suggestions to support the formulation of instruments and strategies that support the market deployment of alternative circular fertiliser.	Non-commercial	Joint (CIC, ACR+, EBA, INAGRO & CETENMA)

	Circular Fertilisers Stakeholders Network (Guidelines and Recommendations)	Contact network of experts that master the topic which can be exploited in the future related discussion.	Non-commercial	Joint (CIC, EBA, Coldiretti, Nuresys & CETENMA)
	Advocacy for policy makers (Skills and know-how)	List of key messages for policy-makers dissemination.	Non-commercial	Joint (CIC, EBA, ACR+ & CETENMA)
EBA (NPO)	Guidelines for fertiliser producers (Plans and strategies)	Compilation of key non-technical, technical, market and regulatory information related to the manufacture of alternative fertilisers.	Non-commercial	Joint (Fer-Play Consortium)
	Recommendations for public administrations (Guidelines and Recommendations)	Practical suggestions in the form of policy briefs to help policy makers to deliver successful strategies and instruments for the market deployment of alternative fertilisers.	Non-commercial	Joint (Fer-Play Consortium)
	Multi-assessment of impacts, trade-offs and framework conditions (Skills and know-how)	Conclusions of the LCSAs and technical + regulatory analysis of the selected alternative fertiliser value chains.	Non-commercial	Joint (Fer-Play Consortium)
NURESYS (SME)	Industrialization potential of alternative fertilisers (Skills and know-how)	Results of the benchmark study of alternative fertilisers and their application technologies with existing fertilisers.	Commercial	Joint (NuReSys, CIC & Cetaqua)
INARGO (RTO)	Database (Data)	Gathers all the info and knowledge the consortium could find on the value chains identified.	Non-commercial	Sole
	Knowledge (Skills and know-how)	Knowledge gained from the project can be used in the future for follow-up projects or other activities.	Non-commercial	Joint (Fer-Play Consortium)
	Guidelines and Advice (Guidelines and Recommendations)	New guidelines and recommendations from the project can be used in the future in daily work.	Non-commercial	Joint (Fer-Play Consortium)
CETAQUA (RTO)	Alternative fertilisers database (Database)	Information submitted by the partners regarding the different value chains studied.	Non-commercial	Joint (Fer-Play Consortium)
	Alternative fertiliser selection	Two stage methodology that allows the selection and classification of alternative	Non-commercial	Joint (WP1 partners)

	methodology (Methods)	fertilisers based on various relevant aspects (nutrient content, toxicity, TRL, etc.).		
	Results of multi- assessment (Skills and know-how)	Selected value chains will be submitted to a rigorous and holistic assessment to determine their environmental, social, economic impacts & trade-offs (via LCSA) as well as their technical and regulatory aspects.	Non-commercial	Joint (WP2 partners)
DRAXIS (SME)	LCA Services (Consulting Services)	LCA consulting services to third parties to various parties, such as individual entrepreneurs, industrial sector, support in R&D actions of universities or European and National funded projects.	Commercial	Sole
REVOLVE (SME)	Comms Impact Reporting, quarterly intern. magazine	Comms agency leader in sustainability communication	Guidelines and best practices in citizen engagement	Expand position in communicating sustainability
ACR+ (SME)	Guidelines for local and regional authorities (Guidelines and recommendations)	Practical suggestions, through policy briefs that could help policy makers deliver successful strategies and instruments for the market deployment of alternative fertilisers.	Non-commercial	Joint (ACR+ & EBA)
NATURLAND (NPO)	Improved knowledge, networks (Guidelines and recommendations)	Knowledge about alternative fertilisers.	Non-commercial	NA
ASAJA (NPO)	New fertilisers (Product)	Use of fertilisers, alternative to traditional fertilization.	Commercial	NA

FER-PLAY partners have identified twenty-four (24) results in total that wish to exploit through the project. Some partners have not identified any exploitable result while others identified multiple. In summary, the majority of the twenty-four results, 50% of them (12) have been declare as "Guidelines and Recommendations", 21% (5) as "Skills and know-how", 13% (3) as "Databases", 4% (1) as "Plans and Strategies", 4% (1) as "Methods", 4% (1) as "Consulting Services" and 4% (1) as "Product".

Out of the 24 results, six results are going to be exploited in a "Commercial" way, while the rest as "Non-commercial". There is one case of IPR related to exploitable results, which refers to Cetaqua and their result "Alternative Fertiliser Database". The type of IPR is a patent for the recovery of phosphorus from organic waste.

Furthermore, the consortium members were asked to describe the market that they intend to provide their results in. The most common answer among partners is farmers, agrifood sector, researchers, and public authorities. The main barriers that partners identified are traditional value chains that are less keen to innovate, inadequate finance and mismatch between market needs. In response to these barriers, partners identified measures to overcome them, with the most common response to be meeting with partners and stakeholders to familiarize the relevant parties with the benefits of their results.

The responses of each project partner regarding their exploitable result(s) are presented in Annex 5 – Exploitation input declared by partners.

6.3. Future Steps

The Exploitation strategy is a dynamic process and changes as the project evolves. Hence, the final version of the Exploitation plan (M30) is foreseen to tackle certain aspects that are not present in this deliverable (i.e. use model of exploitable results, clarification of IPR aspects such as contribution of each partner regarding all the outputs of FER-PLAY, exploitation rights and responsibilities, and funding sources, etc.). Furthermore, the final version of the Exploitation plan will provide updates on the information (e.g. features of exploitable results, value proposition, etc.) presented in this deliverable, due to the fact that as described in Section **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**, it might be the case that some consortium members update or modify their exploitable results, as the project evolves.

Accordingly, a new and enriched version of the Exploitation questionnaire will be developed that will enable the project partners to update their previously submitted input, while providing new information regarding the aforementioned issues that will be analyzed only in the final version of the Exploitation plan (M30). In essence, this new version of the Exploitation questionnaire will contain all the questions depicted in Section 6.1, along with extra questions that will capture the readiness of the results as the later stages of the project. Furthermore, to ensure the exploitation of the project's results, all relevant project partners will be split into groups and Exploitation meetings will be organized, towards the later stages of the project. The aim of those meetings will be to support and guide the consortium members in choosing the most effective exploitation channel for their result.

7. Monitoring

The implementation of the dissemination, communication and exploitation measures are being monitored by the WP leader, EBA, through the reporting spread sheet available in the project's Sharepoint, and attached for information in Annex 1.. The partners will be asked to report on their activities on a regular basis. At the end of the project, the input from periodical reports will be included in the FER-PLAY post-project D&C&E and sustainability plan.

7.1. Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation KPIs

Following key performance indicators (KPIs) presented below will be used to measure the effectiveness of the D&C&E measures.

Table 6. presents the KPIs for the dissemination materials developed throughout the projects.

Table 6. KPIs – Dissemination materials

Dissemination materials	Target audience	KPI	Target
Guidelines for fertiliser end-users.	1	No. guidelines printed & disseminated	At least 1,000
Guidelines for fertiliser producers.	2	No. guidelines printed & disseminated	At least 500
Recommendations for public administrations.	3	No. recommendations elaborated	At least 7
Publications in peer-review journals with open access ensured.	4	No. publications	At least 4
Publications in specialized media.	4, 6	No. articles published	At least 4
Exploitation strategies.	1, 5	No. exploitation strategies developed	At least 2
General dissemination materials	1-6	No. leaflets disseminated	At least 3,000

The Table below presents KPIs for the dissemination activities.

Table 7. KPIs – Dissemination activities

Dissemination channels and activities	Target audience	KPI	Target
Organisation of events (dissemination meetings, congress, seminars and open days) for closer interaction and results presentation to end-users, alternative producers, public administrations and policy makers	1-3	Total No. of stakeholders reached	At least 1,870
Participation in trade fairs (5) & scientific conferences (5), e.g. Ecomondo, Fieragricola, Fruit Attraction, Expo Biogaz, or IWA EcoSTP.	1-6	No. events attended	At least 10
Networking with projects funded under this topic and with other EU project beneficiaries.	6	Total No. of participants	At least 30
Final event.	1-6	No. participants	At least 100

Table 8 presents KPIs that concern communication channels and materials, described in detail in Section 5.

Table 8. KPIs – Communication channels and materials

Channels and materials	KPI	Target
Videos	No. of videos	6
	No. of video views	2000
Infographics	No. of infographics	4
Website	No. of visitors per month	300
Social Media	No. of aggregate followers	1500
Press Releases	No. of press releases	3
Newsletters	No. of newsletters	5
Roll-up, Poster	No. of QR code hits	3000

7.2. Impact reporting

Impact reporting provides ongoing insight into the impact of communication and dissemination activities and will allow WP4 to gauge the effectiveness of the D&E&C Plan. The impact reporting will cover the project KPIs, as outlined above.

Impact Reports:

Three impact reports will be prepared by REVOLVE at the end of M12, M24, and M30, and feeding into the updates for the D&E&C plan (due in M15 and M30) and D4.3 post-project D&E&C Sustainability Plan. A critical aspect of the impact reporting is the feedback of partners via a questionnaire to identify areas for improvement for the coming years of the project.

November 2023 update: M12 Impact Report is attached as Annex 3 and available as a separate document in Sharepoint.

8. EU funding obligations

8.1. Obligation to disseminate results

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner.

Before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the granting authority.

8.2. Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.) and dissemination activities funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Figure 15. European flag with funding statement

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use.

8.3. Open access to scientific publications

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine actionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

8.4. Disclaimer excluding Agency responsibility

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

9. Conclusions

The Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan outlined in this document has been designed to assist project partners in executing the dissemination and communication activities throughout the FER-PLAY project and effectively convey the key messages to the target audiences. This report includes a comprehensive list of all the communication activities planned throughout the project's duration, the communication channels to be utilised for dissemination, and the key messages to be communicated.

The dynamic nature of the project necessitates that the D&C&E Plan will be reviewed and updated continuously in line with the needs and views of stakeholders to ensure that the project's promotion has the maximum impact on the targeted stakeholders, as well as the European community as a whole. As a result, partners have jointly revised the plan to correct deviations in M15. The document will be updated again by M30. In order to extend the project impact beyond the project duration, a 4-year post-project D&C&E sustainability plan will be prepared and presented at the end of the project through D4.3 (M30).

10. References

European Commission (2022). Europe-glossary, 24 February. https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk/europe-glossary/glossary-f_en

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Haardt, J., Weiler, N., Scherer, J. (2019). Making the most of your H2020 project: boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation, Publications Office. European Commission, Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/045684>

Annex 1 – Reporting template

The template is available in the project’s Sharepoint.

Event reporting sheet (for WP₃ and WP₄ events) – one for all partners:

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
Related WP	Related task	Responsible partner	Date (dd/mm/yy)	Place (city, country code)	Name of event	Type of event	Target public	Scope	Joint event with fellow project/platform or FER-PLAY dedicated event? Name of the project	Duration (hours)	Impact: No of participants	
WP4	T4.2.2	INAGRO	02/03/2023	Houthulst, Belgium	Farm-scale anaerobic digestion with field visit	Seminar	Mix	Farm-scale anaerobic digestion and further nutrient recovery (cross checking database interest)	Joint with Boost Pocketvergisting & Nabeverking	3	21	
WP4	T4.2.2	INAGRO	09/03/2023	Alken, Belgium	Farm-scale anaerobic digestion with field visit	Seminar	Mix	Farm-scale anaerobic digestion and further nutrient recovery (cross checking database interest)	Joint with Boost Pocketvergisting & Nabeverking	3	22	
WP3	T3.1	ASAJA	30/05/2023	Madrid (ES)	Fertilization	Seminar	End-users	Discuss about the optimal conditions (from the agronomical and environmental point of view) for the absorption of circular fertilisers	FER-PLAY dedicated	2	30	
WP4	T4.2.1	EBA	30/05/2023	Online	Circular Economy Working Group	Meeting	Producers, academia	Presentation of the FER-PLAY project	An update on Nutri2Cycle project was made as well	2 (full meeting)	34	
					The future of sustainable			FER-PLAY mentioning within	Joint with the Flemish			

Other Dissemination and Communication activities – individual for each partner:

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
Partner (Choose from the drop-down list)	Type of activity (Choose between Dissemination of results or Communication about the project)	Category of activity (Choose the activity from the drop-down list)	Title of publication, website article, video, newsletter etc. (In case of a social media post, make sure to specify the social media platform used, e.g Twitter, LinkedIn)	Status of the activity (Choose between Delivered/Planned)	Date of publication (actual or scheduled)	Target public (Indicate all types)	Number of people reached	Short description of the activity	Relevant link	Other comments
ACR+	Communication	Website post	About FER-PLAY	Delivered	15/09/2022	Public administration; general public	Around 3000/month		https://acrplus.org/en/activities/acr-projects/2-content/3741-ferplay	
ACR+	Communication	Press release/Newsletter	Be a part of ACR+ Sustainable Food Systems projects	Delivered	10/10/2022	Public administration	490		https://acrplus.org/en/news/acr-news/3549-be-a-part-of-acr-sustainable-food-systems-projects	
ACR+	Communication	Press release/Newsletter	Sustainable Food Systems Answer our survey to be part of our next projects!	Delivered	17/10/2022	Public administration	490		https://acrplus.org/en/news/acr-news/3562-sustainable-food-systems-answer-our-survey-to-be-part-of-our-next-projects	
ACR+	Communication	Press release/Newsletter	"Soils, where food begins", ACR+ supports World Soil Day	Delivered	05/12/2022	Public administration	490		https://acrplus.org/en/news/acr-news/3648-soils-where-food-begins-acr-supports-world-soil-day	
ACR+	Communication	Press release/Newsletter	FER-PLAY Share your experience on alternative fertilisers	Delivered	13/03/2023	Public administration	490		https://acrplus.org/en/news/acr-news/3790-fer-play-share-your-experience-on-alternative-fertilisers	
ACR+	Dissemination	Website post	FER-PLAY Highlight	Delivered	21/06/2023	Public administration; general public	Around 3000/month		https://acrplus.org/en/activities/acr-projects/2-content/3741-ferplay	

Annex 2 – Visual identity

fer▶play

Visual Identity Guidelines
December 2022

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Introduction

The FER-PLAY visual identity plays an essential role in promoting the project; as such, it is imperative to respect these guidelines when using the logo, font and colours for any external or internal communication, such as presentation templates, posters, business cards, flyers, social media, and so on.

The following guidelines provide a framework for using the brand identity in a consistent manner. Consistency communicates reliability and provides the foundation for working together in an efficient way. While maintaining the highest quality standard, our choice of words and images are opportunities to show that we understand and engage with our audiences.

These visual identity guidelines are a living document and may be updated to accommodate changing requirements. If you require assistance, additional support materials, or adjustments for a specific situation, please contact the FER-PLAY team. Likewise, if for any reason, you need to work outside the scope of these visual identity guidelines, please contact the Communication leads.

FER-PLAY
Visual Identity Guidelines

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The logo

About the logo and its meaning

Rationale

FER-PLAY will map and assess alternative fertilisers made from secondary raw materials, such as manure, and highlight their multiple benefits in order to promote their wide-scale production and use on field.

The FER-PLAY logo aims to represent the project goals:

- The soil patch and wheat stalk represent agriculture, and the importance of quality soil in plant growth.
- The "play" icon implies action, change.

The logo

Logo colour variations

Main logo
This is the default version of the logo, to be used on white or light backgrounds.

Black
This version of the logo is to be used on black and white layouts or documents, on light backgrounds.

Negative
This version of the logo is to be used on colored backgrounds and photographs. Be careful that the logo needs to stand out against the background.

Negative white
This version of the logo is only to be used on darker colored backgrounds and photographs, when the color negative does not stand out enough against the background.

The logo

Safe area and minimum sizes

Safe area
Keep all other graphic elements, logos or margins at a minimum distance as defined by the "Safe area" line. The minimum space around the wordmark is equal to the height of the "f".

Minimum sizes
The minimum size is indicated by the length of the logo. The logo should never be smaller than the minimum indicated sizes to avoid compromising its visibility.

Printing
The width of the logo should never be smaller than 25 mm.

Digital media
The width of the logo should never be smaller than 70 px.

Colours

The project has an extended colour palette to meet all communication needs

PEAR
CMYK: 50, 10, 95, 0
RGB: 149, 181, 49
HEX: # 95B531

SEAWEED
CMYK: 70, 50, 100, 45
RGB: 69, 78, 51
HEX: # 45A21F

KHAKI
CMYK: 25, 25, 45, 5
RGB: 198, 180, 145
HEX: # C4B491

COCONUT
CMYK: 55, 60, 70, 25
RGB: 147, 96, 69
HEX: # 956045

BLUE GREY
CMYK: 45, 20, 25, 0
RGB: 155, 182, 187
HEX: # 9BB6BB

SLATE GREY
CMYK: 75, 50, 40, 50
RGB: 66, 92, 107
HEX: # 425C6B

CANTALOUPE
CMYK: 0, 35, 55, 5
RGB: 259, 177, 120
HEX: # EFB17B

TUSCANY
CMYK: 10, 75, 85, 5
RGB: 211, 88, 47
HEX: # D55B2F

FER-PLAY
Visual Identity Guidelines

7

Messages

Tagline and golden paragraph to describe the project

Tagline

**Alternative fertilisers
for circularity & soil health**

Golden paragraph

FER-PLAY is facilitating the uptake of alternative fertilisers to protect ecosystems, decrease EU dependence on fertiliser imports, foster circularity, and improve soil health. The project will map and assess alternative fertilisers made from secondary raw materials, such as manure, and highlight their multiple benefits in order to promote their wide-scale production and use on field.

FER-PLAY
Visual Identity Guidelines

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Typography

The typeface used for FER-PLAY communications is **Fieldwork**

FER-PLAY

Fieldwork Geo Bold

Alternative fertilisers for circularity & soil health

Fieldwork Geo DemiBold

FER-PLAY is facilitating the uptake of alternative fertilisers, to protect ecosystems, decrease EU dependence on fertiliser imports, foster circularity and improve soil health. The project will map and assess alternative fertilisers made from secondary raw materials, such as manure, and highlight their multiple benefits in order to promote their wide-scale production and use on field.

Fieldwork Geo Regular
Minimum font size for body text: 9pt

FER-PLAY is facilitating the uptake of alternative fertilisers, to protect ecosystems, decrease EU dependence on fertiliser imports, foster circularity and improve soil health. The project will map and assess alternative fertilisers made from secondary raw materials, such as manure, and highlight their multiple benefits in order to promote their wide-scale production and use on field.

Fieldwork Geo Light
Minimum font size for body text: 9pt

Typography

When the recommended typeface is not available, FER-PLAY communications are to use the font **Corbel**

FER-PLAY

Corbel Bold

Alternative fertilisers for circularity & soil health

FER-PLAY is facilitating the uptake of alternative fertilisers, to protect ecosystems, decrease EU dependence on fertiliser imports, foster circularity and improve soil health. The project will map and assess alternative fertilisers made from secondary raw materials, such as manure, and highlight their multiple benefits in order to promote their wide-scale production and use on field.

Corbel Regular
Minimum font size for body text: 9pt

Additional branding

Other logos and mentions to include in FER-PLAY communications

As a Horizon Europe funded project, FER-PLAY communication activities and products must also include the EU flag and following disclaimer:

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor REA can be held responsible for them.

Visual elements to use in FER-PLAY design

The "play" icon can be used as a decorative graphic element in FER-PLAY communications, in solid colors or as a picture frame. The use of illustrations with a "hand-drawn" style is also recommended.

FER-PLAY
Visual Identity Guidelines

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Contact

For any questions regarding these guidelines, please contact the communication partner:

Contact person

Ayça Al Marhubi
Communications Manager
REVOLVE
ayca@revolve.media

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Visual Identity Guidelines

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Annex 3 – Impact report M12

The report is available as a separate document in the project's Sharepoint.

Introduction

- This Impact Report summarizes the outreach activities and their impact numbers during the first year of FER-PLAY (September 2022 – August 2023).
- The purpose is to have the annual overview and to enhance the long-term impact of this Horizon Europe project to adjusting our tactics along the way.
- The findings are compiled by REVOLVE and European Biogas Association (EBA). Any errors in the reporting are the responsibility of these organizations and do not reflect the opinions of the FER-PLAY partners.

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KPIs

Channels and materials	KPI	Target	Year 1 values
Videos	No. of videos	6	1
	No. of video views	2000	451
Infographics	No. of infographics	4	1
Website	No. of visitors per month	300	629
Social Media	No. of aggregate followers	1500	594
Press Releases	No. of press releases	3	1
Newsletters	No. of newsletters	5	2
Roll-up, Poster	No. of QR code hits	3000	TBD

2

Dissemination events

*As in Grant Agreement

Planned date	Activity	Target group	Responsible partner	Status
M7	Seminar for farmers and technicians	Fertiliser users	INAGRO	Completed
M10	2 Network meetings with fertilisers producers	Fertiliser producers	(1 EBA, 1 CIC)	Completed
M13	Open days/field demonstrations	Fertiliser users	NuReSys & INAGRO	Nov/Dec 2023
M14	2 Workshops for organic and young farmers	Fertiliser users	(1 NATURLAND, 1 ASAJA)	NATURLAND – planned for 1 December
M20	Workshop for other EU project coordinators	EU project consortia	CETENMA	Expected May 24
M25	Seminar for farmers and technicians	Fertiliser users	INAGRO	Expected Sep 24
M25	Open days/field demonstrations	Fertiliser users	NuReSys & INAGRO	Expected Sep 24
M28	Workshop for local and regional authorities	Local administration	ACR+	Expected Dec 24
M28	Policy webinar	Policy makers	EBA	Expected Dec 24
M28	2 Workshops for organic and young farmers	Fertiliser users	(1 NATURLAND, 1 ASAJA)	Expected Dec 24
M29	Workshop for decision makers from EU regions	Local administration	ACR+	Expected Jan 25
M30	2 Network webinars with fertilisers producers	Fertiliser producers	(1 EBA, 1 CIC)	Expected Feb 25
M30	Final event	ALL	REVOLVE	Expected Feb 25
TBC	Webinar for COPA-COGECA members	Fertiliser users	COLDIRETTI	?

M25 Guidelines for producers and end-users, Recommendations for public administrations

3

Other dissemination activities

Activity	Task	Target group	Responsible partners	Status
Organisation of 3 congresses		Fertiliser producers	CIC (2), EBA (1)	CIC at Ecomondo - completed
Participation in 5 international trade fairs		Fertiliser producers	CIC (2), CETAQUA (2), EBA (1)	2 achieved (CIC – Sanatech, Ecomondo)
4 articles in sectoral magazines (fertilisers sector)		Fertiliser producers	CIC	2 published (Acqua ed energia, Fertiliser Focus)
Participation in World Soil Day (5 th Dec) within ECN		Fertilisers producers	CIC	tbd
4 publications in peer-review journals with open access		Scientific community	CETENMA	tbd
Participation in 5 scientific congresses		Scientific community	CETENMA (2), CETAQUA (2), EBA (1)	1 achieved (CETENMA - ESNI)

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Website Overview year 1

Data Analysis Dashboard

ENGAGEMENT RATE:

46%

AVERAGE NUMBER OF USERS/MONTH:

91

UNIQUE VISITOR TOP 3 LOCATIONS:

1. Belgium
2. Spain
3. USA
4. Turkey
5. Germany

TOTAL USERS SINCE JANUARY 2023:

812

MOST USED KEYWORDS:

Ferplay
Fer play
Fer-play

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Website Overview 2023 Q3 Jul-Aug-Sep

Data Analysis Dashboard

ENGAGEMENT RATE:

90%

AVERAGE NUMBER OF USERS/MONTH:

129

UNIQUE VISITOR TOP 3 LOCATIONS:

1. Spain
2. Belgium
3. France
4. Israel
5. Italy

TOTAL USERS July-September 2023:

387

MOST USED KEYWORDS:

Ferplay
Fer play
Fer-play

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Twitter

TOTAL FOLLOWERS
(Year 1):

172

ENGAGEMENT
RATE:**

5.65%

**Engagement rates are calculated as a quarterly average and measure the likes, shares, and comments to evaluate content quality.

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LinkedIn

TOTAL FOLLOWERS
(Year 1):

422

GROWTH RATE for
Quarter 3 (Jul-Sep
2023):*

10.46%

ENGAGEMENT
RATE (Year 1):**

7.124%

*Annual growth rate is calculated as an average of the 12 months together.

**Engagement rates are calculated as a quarterly average and measure the likes, shares, and comments to evaluate content quality.

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Newsletter

UNIQUE OPENS OF THE NEWSLETTER:

0078

TOTAL SUBSCRIBERS SINCE 09/2022:

0073

TOP 5 LOCATIONS BY OPENS:

1. Belgium
2. Spain
3. USA
4. Germany

The **A**lternative

FER-PLAY assesses seven promising alternative fertilisers value chains

Several innovative alternative fertilisers **value chains** appeared in recent years as promising replacements for conventional fertilisers. After collecting data of **48 different alternative fertilisers** value chains (check out our [database!](#)), FER-PLAY scored them and ranked the **7 most promising** and better characterised value chains that represent the variability of agricultural applications and practices across Europe. Some of the outcoming fertilisers are well-known since long time ago (stabilised sludge, compost and solid fraction of digestate), while others (struvite, chompost and feather meal) represent more recent proposals. FER-PLAY will contribute to tackle the market uptake challenges for these alternative fertilisers.

Urban waste water

Struvite

Videos

TOTAL VIEWS:

451

Number of videos: 1 video on YouTube

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Media Relations

FER-PLAY in the press

NUMBER OF MEDIA HITS:

0010

HIGHEST MEDIA COVERAGE:

1. Spain
2. USA
3. Netherlands
4. Belgium
5. Italy

[ElEspañol](#) (Spain), [Head Topics](#) (USA), [CROEM](#) (Spain), [Murcia.com](#) (Spain), [CARM.es](#) (Spain), [Cartagena Actualidad](#) (Spain), [Murcia Actualidad](#) (Spain).

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Outreach

PARTICIPATION IN EXTERNAL NEWSLETTERS

BioRefine News Bulletin – September 2023

Novafert Newsletter - May 2023

B-Ferst Newsletter - May 2023

Updates from the sister projects

ferplay Facilitating the uptake of alternative fertilisers, to protect ecosystems, decrease EU dependence on fertiliser imports, foster circularity and improve soil health.

[Website](#)

A new database for alternative fertiliser value chain!

FER-PLAY consortium launched a database that collects all available data from 61 value chains derived from 7 secondary raw materials. When accessing this database, you can quickly navigate to the information category that is most relevant for you.

[Find it here](#)

FER-PLAY is taking parts to some interesting events

<p>June 21st - European Compost Network</p>		
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Annex 4 – Exploitation questionnaire

This questionnaire has been developed with the aim of capturing all the needed information regarding the exploitation plan of each partner. In Figure 1 and Figure 2 the Exploitation questionnaire is presented. As seen below, there are four subsections which are dedicated to identifying the exploitable result(s) of each project partner, a short description of the exploitable result, IP issues regarding the development of the result and finally a market analysis section which tries to identify the relevant market that the project partner aims to offer the result.

EXPLOITATION	INPUT FROM PARTNER X		GUIDANCE
Identification of exploitable results			
Does any project result , connected to the activities of your organization in the project, have potential for exploitation?	Please select		Project results: Results are any tangible or intangible effects of the project's action, such as data, know-how or information, whether or not they can be protected, as well as any rights attached to them, including intellectual property rights. Project results can be reusable and exploitable (e.g. inventions, prototypes, services) as such, or elements (knowledge, technology, processes, networks) that have potential to contribute for further work on research or innovation. A Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.
If yes, how many exploitable results can you identify?	Please select		If you have identified two or more exploitable results, please copy the entire column D & E on the right side and reply to the following questions separately for each exploitable result.
If no, please explain why.			If no, you may go afterwards to the next section.
Description of exploitable results			
Please select among the available exploitable result types, the one that best matches your exploitable result.	N/R	If other, please briefly explain:	Please indicate a proper title for your result.
Please provide a title and a short description of your exploitable result, including its main features and value proposition.	Title: Short Description Main features: Objectives: Value proposition: Advantages: Main use: Alternative uses: What is new: Why is important: What needs does it meet:		To allow a better characterization of the project results, we have proceeded with the below grouping into 8 distinct categories. Options: Technological solutions (e.g. hardware, infrastructure, equipment, product, software); Methods (methodologies, protocols, operational procedures, processes); Models and algorithms ; Skills and know-how (expertise in carrying out assessments/analyses e.g. carbon footprint, water footprint, climate risk, running models, etc.); Guidelines and recommendations (for policy) (e.g. for legislation, society (e.g. a nutritional model, industry, etc.); Plans and strategies ; Data ; Standards (standardisation activities).
What is the intended type of exploitation (e.g. commercial, non-commercial). If other, please briefly explain.	Please select	If other, please briefly explain:	Use approximately 250 words to describe your project result elaborating on its main features and its value proposition (including objectives, advantages, main use, alternative uses, what is new, why is important, what needs does it meet).
Ownership and protection of the results			
Is there any background Intellectual Property (IP) related to the exploitable result? If yes,	Please select		Options: Commercial exploitation (such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities); Non-commercial (policy-making, policy advice, further research, educational purposes, etc.); Other (any other possible exploitation that deserves attention for their output).
a. Please describe background IP			Intellectual Property refers to the creations of the mind, such as inventions, literary and artistic works, designs, and symbols, names and images used in commerce.
b. Is your background IP protected with some form of Intellectual Property Right (IPR)?			Background IP refers to any IP that is held by project beneficiaries before entering into the agreement and that is needed to implement the project or to exploit project results.
c. If yes please indicate how	Please select	If other please specify:	Intellectual Property Rights are private legal rights that protect the creation of the human mind: inventions, literary and artistic works, and symbols, names, images, and designs used in commerce.
Are you the exclusive owner of the exploitable result?	Please select		Intellectual Property Rights (e.g. patents, copyright and related rights, trade marks, trade secrets etc.). More specifically, a patent is an exclusive right granted for the protection of inventions (products or processes) offering a new technical solution or facilitating a new way of doing something; copyright (or author's right) is the term used to describe the rights that creators have over their literary, scientific and artistic works; a utility model is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which allows its owner to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without their authorisation, for a limited period of time; a trade mark is an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to the goods and services for which it is registered; a trade secrets agreement offers right holders protection when it comes to confidential information that can be sold or licensed; a patent grants protection to the content of a database preventing the extraction and/or reuse of the whole or substantial part of its content when the structure of a database is not an original creation. For further information you may consult Your Guide to IP in Europe of The European IP Helpdesk (link: https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.eu/en/your-guide-to-ip-in-europe/).
If no, please name the other partner(s) that are owner(s) of this result.			Results are owned by the beneficiary that generates them. Two or more beneficiaries own results jointly if: (a) they have jointly generated them and (b) it is not possible to: (i) establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or (ii) separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection.
Do you intend to protect your result with some form of Intellectual Property Right (IPR)?	Please select		Intellectual Property Rights are private legal rights that protect the creation of the human mind: inventions, literary and artistic works, and symbols, names, images, and designs used in commerce.
If yes, please specify how.	Please select	If other please specify:	Intellectual Property Rights (e.g. patents, copyright and related rights, trade marks, trade secrets etc.). More specifically, a patent is an exclusive right granted for the protection of inventions (products or processes) offering a new technical solution or facilitating a new way of doing something; copyright (or author's right) is the term used to describe the rights that creators have over their literary, scientific and artistic works; a utility model is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which allows its owner to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without their authorisation, for a limited period of time; a trade mark is an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to

Figure 1: Identification and description of exploitable results. FER-PLAY Exploitation questionnaire

Market Research			
Have you identified the potential market(s) of your result? If yes, please specify.	Please select	If yes please specify:	e.g. Environmental protection consulting services, Environmental technical/engineering solutions, etc.
Who are the main potential customers and/or end-users who could be interested in this result? Please describe in more detail.	Please select	If more than one, please indicate: Please describe your selected options.	The distinction is that an end-user is someone who completes the final purchase of a product, while a customer can purchase a product and then resell it. It can be the case that someone is both the purchaser and the end user of a product.
Are there any competitive solutions to your result? Please describe (including pros and cons compared to your result).	Please select	Please describe:	They could be commercial solutions, research results, projects or other. Please explain the pros and cons of the your result(s) against the other concepts/solutions existing in the market.
Are there any barriers to the uptake of your result?		Please elaborate:	e.g. inadequate financing, skills shortages, regulation that hinders innovation, intellectual property right issues, traditional value chains that are less keen to innovate, incompatibility between parts of systems (lack of standards), mismatch between market needs and the solution
Are there any measures to overcome these barriers?		Please elaborate:	e.g. meetings with policy makers, alternative ways of financing, training sessions with the relevant parties, etc.

Figure 2: Market analysis aspects. FER-PLAY Exploitation questionnaire

The questionnaire above has been developed to capture as much information as possible at this stage of the project. As the project progresses, more information will be available to project partners regarding their result(s), thus an updated version will be delivered to partners to gather the additional information.

Annex 5 – Exploitation input declared by partners

10.1.1. CETENMA

CETENMA has identified five (5) potential results that intends to exploit after the end of the project. Below these results are presented, along with the input that the partner provided.

10.1.1.1. RESULT NUMBER 1: ALTERNATIVE FERTILISERS DATABASE

Alternative Fertilisers Database

Declared by	CETENMA
Type of Exploitable Result	Database
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Alternative fertilisers database</p> <p>Short Description: Open-access database on alternative fertiliser value chains</p> <p>Main features: Data on 60 alternative fertiliser value chains</p> <p>Objectives: Mapping alternative fertilisers</p> <p>Value proposition: Organized information covering a wide range of alternative fertilisers value chains characteristics</p> <p>Main use: Research</p> <p>Alternative uses: Policy makers, industry</p>
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	<p>By Multiple Partners: INAGRO, CIC, EBA, NURESYS, CETAQUA, ACR+, COLDIRETTI, NATURLAND, ASAJA</p> <p>The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.</p>

Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Fertiliser production sector and the Agrifood sector
Potential Customers	Researchers, private sector and industry
Barriers	Mismatch between market needs and the solution
Mitigation Measures	None at the moment

10.1.1.2. RESULT NUMBER 2: ENVIRONMENTAL LCA

Environmental LCA

Declared by	CETENMA
Type of Exploitable Result	Consulting Services
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Environmental Life Cycle Assessment</p> <p>Short Description: Evaluation of 7 circular fertiliser value chains based on their environmental impacts</p> <p>Main features:</p> <p>Objectives: Identifying the most relevant environmental impacts of producing the circular fertilisers along the valorisation of 7 secondary raw materials</p> <p>Value proposition: Analyzing the impacts on different categories to evaluate their positive effects on the environment and compare their differences with other raw materials</p> <p>Advantages:</p> <p>Main use: Decision making and detect the main hotspots to improve the processes from an environmental point of view</p> <p>Alternative uses: Increasing the awareness/knowledge of society about circular fertiliser</p> <p>What is new: The seven circular fertiliser value chains for the LCAs were selected after performing a screening methodology composed of two steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Go/no go --> Several value chains were discarded based on their characteristics

- Scoring --> Those value chains that passed the go/no go classification were evaluated

Type of Exploitation	Commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	By Multiple Partners: FER-PLAY Consortium The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Fertiliser production sector and the Agrifood sector
Potential Customers	Industry: Policymakers, public and private entities, researchers Justification: These stakeholders may be interested in the results of the LCAs since the studies will show the impacts and benefits of producing/using circular fertilisers. For instance, this is interesting to create/modify the legal framework, spread information and improve the production processes, among others.
Barriers	Skills shortages Both policymakers and citizens may not have the required skills to understand the results obtained.
Mitigation Measures	Creation of workshops and meetings with the relevant stakeholders to present the results and the benefits of the approach. In addition, creation specific workshops with technical stakeholders to get them familiar with the approach. (PROPOSED BY DRAXIS)

10.1.1.3. RESULT NUMBER 3: SOCIAL LCA

Social LCA

Declared by	CETENMA
Type of Exploitable Result	Consulting Services
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Social Life Cycle Assessment</p> <p>Short Description: By using the PSILCA database, the 7 value chains will be evaluated bearing in mind different stakeholders like society, local community and workers</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluating the 7 circular fertiliser value chains using the PSILCA database to establish a starting point for the production of circular fertilisers - Assessing the positive and negative impacts of each alternative fertiliser value chain from raw material extraction to use (ideally) at country/sector level <p>Value proposition: Analyzing the impacts on different stakeholders and social indicators to evaluate their positive and negative social impacts</p> <p>Advantages:</p> <p>Main use: Decision making and detect the main hotspots to improve the processes from a social perspective</p> <p>Alternative uses: Increasing the awareness/knowledge of society about circular fertiliser social impacts</p> <p>What is new:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The database consulted is incomplete for the project value chains and, thus, a database is being created to address this issue - Some types of surveys are being conducted in order to gather information from 3 stakeholders: end-users, producers and policy-makers. These surveys will feed part of the S-LCA
Type of Exploitation	Commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	<p>By Multiple Partners: FER-PLAY Consortium</p> <p>The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA</p>

Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Fertiliser production sector and the Agrifood sector
Potential Customers	<p>Industry: Policymakers, public and private entities, researchers</p> <p>Justification: These stakeholders may be interested in the results of the LCAs since the studies will show the impacts and benefits of producing/using circular fertilisers. For instance, this is interesting to create/modify the legal framework, spread information and improve the production processes, among others.</p>
Barriers	<p>Skills shortages</p> <p>Both policymakers and citizens may not have the required skills to understand the results obtained.</p>
Mitigation Measures	Creation of workshops and meetings with the relevant stakeholders to present the results and the benefits of the approach. In addition, creation specific workshops with technical stakeholders to get them familiar with the approach. (PROPOSED BY DRAXIS)

10.1.1.4. RESULT NUMBER 4: ECONOMIC LCA

Economic LCA

Declared by	CETENMA
Type of Exploitable Result	Guidelines and Recommendations
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Life Cycle Cost Assessment</p> <p>Short Description: An analysis in terms of costs related to the 7 circular fertiliser value chains will be performed. This kind of assessment involves all the costs, including acquisition, operation, maintenance and disposal costs.</p> <p>Objectives: Determining the parts of the value chains where the process can be improved from an economic point of view.</p>

Value proposition: The cost optimization can also be determined in the different stages of the circular fertiliser production process.

Main use: Defining the total costs of a product during its life cycle, considering the costs of the different actors involved and identifying opportunities for improvement.

Type of Exploitation	Commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	By Multiple Partners: FER-PLAY Consortium The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Fertiliser production sector and the Agrifood sector
Potential Customers	Industry: Policymakers, public and private entities, researchers Justification: These stakeholders may be interested in the results of the LCAs since the studies will show the impacts and benefits of producing/using circular fertilisers. For instance, this is interesting to create/modify the legal framework, spread information and improve the production processes, among others.
Barriers	Skills shortages Both policymakers and citizens may not have the required skills to understand the results obtained.
Mitigation Measures	Creation of workshops and meetings with the relevant stakeholders to present the results and the benefits of the approach. In addition, creation specific workshops with technical stakeholders to get them familiar with the approach. (PROPOSED BY DRAXIS)

10.1.1.5. RESULT NUMBER 5: SUSTAINABILITY LCA

Sustainability LCA

Declared by	CETENMA
Type of Exploitable Result	Consulting Services
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment</p> <p>Short Description: the three kinds of assessment is combined as one to evaluate the three pillars of sustainability: economics, environment, and society.</p> <p>Objectives: Identifying the negative impacts and benefits of the processes involved in the circular fertiliser value chains considering the economic, environmental and social point of view.</p> <p>Value proposition: Potential and future decision-makers, stakeholders, enterprises and consumers can benefit from SLCA</p> <p>Main use: Increasing the citizens' awareness and decision-makers by organizing the economic, environmental and social information related to circular fertiliser production.</p>
Type of Exploitation	Commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	<p>By Multiple Partners: FER-PLAY Consortium</p> <p>The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.</p>
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Fertiliser production sector and the Agrifood sector
Potential Customers	Industry: Policymakers, public and private entities, researchers

Justification: These stakeholders may be interested in the results of the LCAs since the studies will show the impacts and benefits of producing/using circular fertilisers. For instance, this is interesting to create/modify the legal framework, spread information and improve the production processes, among others.

Barriers	Skills shortages Both policymakers and citizens may not have the required skills to understand the results obtained.
Mitigation Measures	Creation of workshops and meetings with the relevant stakeholders to present the results and the benefits of the approach. In addition, creation specific workshops with technical stakeholders to get them familiar with the approach. (PROPOSED BY DRAXIS)

10.1.2. CIC

CIC has identified five (5) potential results that intends to exploit after the end of the project. Below these results are presented, along with the input that the partner provided.

10.1.2.1. RESULT NUMBER 1: A PRACTICAL HANDBOOK FOR CIRCULAR FERTILISERS USE

A practical handbook for circular fertilisers use

Declared by	CIC
Type of Exploitable Result	Guidelines and Recommendations
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: A practical handbook for circular fertilisers use (D3.1 Guidelines for end-users)</p> <p>Short Description: with the information collected and elaborated during WP3 and WP2 a deliverable (D3.1 Guidelines for end-users) is going to be produced, this will be divulged to farmers and technicians.</p> <p>Main features: it will contain a description of the different circular fertilisers, their characteristics (nutrient status, amending effects...) and application modality and machinery required for their uses, other than the value chains from which they are produced.</p>

Objectives: Increasing the use of circular fertilisers by farmers, not only through a better knowledge of their uses though also thanks a better awareness of the importance of recycling nutrients and organic matter.

Value proposition: The handbook will contain information collected by FERPLAY consortium from major experts of each field of circular fertilisers in EU. The quality of its content is supposed to be quite high.

Advantages: The handbook will be both technical and easy to approach, thanks to the participation of farmers' association, which can provide the best approach to improve the practical use of the manual.

Main use: Farmers will have a handbook to explain the differences between circular fertilisers and their use.

Alternative uses: The manual will increase awareness, both for farmers and for general stakeholders, in the importance of circular fertilisers use, considering the environmental, economic and health scopes.

What is new: The manual will include different circular fertilisers in the same document, letting its users compare their uses and characteristics.

Why is important: At now many farmers and technician are still reluctant to use circular fertilisers, that's for different reasons: they don't master the practice of these fertilisers, they fear the presence of contaminants or simply they are used to traditional fertilisers. Hopefully this handbook will increase the use of circular fertiliser closing knowledge gap on the topic.

What needs does it meet: Often there is a knowledge gap between circular fertilisers producers, researchers and end uses, the aim of this handbook will be to close it.

Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	CIC, NATURLAND, ASAJA, COLDIRETTI, INAGRO & CETENMA The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Farmers and agriculture technicians
Potential Customers	Private Sector, farmers and agriculture technicians

Barriers	<p>Traditional value chains that are less keen to innovate.</p> <p>Farmers and technicians can be reluctant to use circular fertilisers, and this handbook as consequence.</p>
Mitigation Measures	<p>Thanks to the help of farmers associations which are part of the FERPLAY consortium we intend to make a product which is easy to use, appealing and trustworthy for farmers and technicians.</p>

10.1.2.2. RESULT NUMBER 2: A PRACTICAL HANDBOOK FOR CIRCULAR FERTILISERS PRODUCTION

A practical handbook for circular fertilisers production

Declared by	CIC
Type of Exploitable Result	Guidelines and Recommendations
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: A practical handbook for circular fertilisers production (D3.2 Guidelines for producers)</p> <p>Short Description: with the information collected and elaborated during WP3 and WP2 a deliverable (D3.2 Guidelines for producers) is going to be produced, this will be divulged to circular fertilisers producers or the ones who would like to start this business activity, mainly compost producers on our side.</p> <p>Main features: The guidelines will focus on commercial and regulatory drivers to permits obtainment and for raising awareness of end-users, instruments for the improvement of cost-benefit ratio and how to gain acceptance of the production facility in the territory.</p> <p>Objectives: Indirectly increase the use of circular fertiliser by facilitating circular fertilisers producers in managing regulatory drivers and communication with the end users.</p> <p>Value proposition: The handbook will contain information collected by FERPLAY consortium from major experts of each field of circular fertilisers in EU. The quality of its content is supposed to be quite high.</p> <p>Advantages: Thanks to the participation of circular fertiliser producer association to the FERPLAY consortium, the handbook will meet the real need of the companies involved in the recycling of nutrient and organic matter for the agriculture or AIMING to enter this market.</p> <p>Main use: The handbook will help circular fertilisers producers to deal with the actual legislation, to communicate the advantages of these product to the farmers and, eventually, to increase the quality and sustainability of their products.</p>

Alternative uses: The manual will increase awareness, both for producers and for general stakeholders, in the importance of circular fertilisers use, considering the environmental, economic and health scopes.

What is new: The handbook will be elaborated with the joint work of farmers associations, producers' associations and legislation experts, producing a document that faces the topic all-round.

Why is important: A better knowledge of the legislation and users need will greatly help the producers in the selling/supplying process.

What needs does it meet: Although the technical know-how is mastered by producers, still there are issues in the communication with the final users and in supplying them.

Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	CIC, EBA, NURESYS, COLDIRETTI & CETENMA The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Producers of circular fertilisers
Potential Customers	Private Sector, Producers of circular fertilisers
Barriers	Traditional value chains that are less keen to innovate. A small minority of producers can be more interested in the waste management side of the value chain, rather than in the fertilisers production and use.
Mitigation Measures	This handbook also will sensitize producers to the importance of the circularity of nutrient and organic matter.

10.1.2.3. RESULT NUMBER 3: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PUBLIC ADMINISTRATIONS

Recommendations for public administrations

Declared by	CIC
Type of Exploitable Result	Guidelines and Recommendations
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Recommendations for public administrations (D3.3)</p> <p>Short Description: with the information collected and elaborated during WP3 and WP2 a deliverable (D3.3) is going to be produced, this will be divulged to policy makers.</p> <p>Main features: The recommendations, in the form of policy briefs, will be practical suggestions to support the formulation of instruments and strategies that support the market deployment of alternative circular fertiliser.</p> <p>Objectives: Helping the policy makers that don't have the technical know-how to master the issue of circular fertilisers to make the right decision to foster circularity in agriculture/food/waste sector.</p> <p>Value proposition: The handbook will contain information collected by FERPLAY consortium from major experts of each field of circular fertilisers in EU. The quality of its content is supposed to be quite high.</p> <p>Advantages: Thanks to the participation of producers, users and researchers of circular fertilisers to the FERPLAY consortium the Recommendations will represent all points of view.</p> <p>Main use: The recommendations will be used as a technical handbook by policymakers at all level, from local institution to EU politicians, to get the essential information on the advantages of circular fertilisers production and use.</p> <p>Alternative uses: The manual will increase awareness, both for policy makers and for general stakeholders, in the importance of circular fertilisers use, considering the environmental, economic and health scopes.</p> <p>What is new: The handbook will be elaborated with the joint work of farmers associations, producers' associations, and legislation experts, producing a document that faces the topic all-round.</p> <p>Why is important: Policymakers have a great importance to foster the recycling process of nutrient and organic matter, they consequently should have the essential technical knowledge to face the topic and better improve this virtuous process.</p> <p>What needs does it meet: Policy makers can lack the appropriate technical knowledge to deeply understand advantages and issues in the production and use of circular fertilisers.</p>
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial

Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	CIC, ACR+, EBA, INAGRO & CETENMA The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Policy makers in the field of agriculture and environment
Potential Customers	Policy makers in the field of agriculture and environment
Barriers	Regulations that hinder innovation Uncertainty on the political decisions/regulations
Mitigation Measures	None at the moment

10.1.2.4. RESULT NUMBER 4: CIRCULAR FERTILISERS STAKEHOLDERS NETWORK

Circular Fertilisers Stakeholders Network

Declared by	CETENMA
Type of Exploitable Result	Skills and know-how
Title, Short Description and Main Features	Title: Circular Fertilisers Stakeholders Network Short Description: During WP3 task 3.2 - Co-creation with alternative fertilisers producers, five focus groups will be set up, with at least 10 members each. Contacting these experts will create a network of

professionals that master the topic which can be exploited in the future related discussion.

Main features: the members of the 5 focus groups should be experts in the field of circular fertilisers, related with one or more of the following topics: environmental, social, economic, technical and regulatory. Moreover, they should represent all the following groups: associations, public institutions, technicians and university.

Objectives: the objective is to keep in touch with the experts contacted during the setup of the focus group, to have exploit the network for future need of expertise.

Value proposition: The expert should all round cover the world of circular fertiliser with a wide knowledge of their production, use, and research.

Advantages: they are providers of knowledge and expertise

Main use: for discussions or relevant information request, open discussion, policy advocacy papers

Alternative uses:

What is new: the group of stakeholders have never met

Why is important: they own knowledge

What needs does it meet: request of information

Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	CIC, EBA, Coldiretti, Nuresys & CETENMA The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Not identified.
Potential Customers	All partners might be interested in the network.
Barriers	The barrier would be the lack of time of these stakeholders to dedicate to the necessities.

Mitigation Measures

Using the network only for interesting purposes.

10.1.2.5. RESULT NUMBER 5: ADVOCACY FOR POLICY MAKERS

Advocacy for policy makers

Declared by	CIC
Type of Exploitable Result	Plans and strategies
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Advocacy for policy makers</p> <p>Short Description: All guidelines are gathering the knowledge from WP2 and dissemination events. The main key messages can be exploited in advocacy documents to policy makers to enhance the use of circular fertilisers.</p> <p>Main features: Only key and relevant messages will be used</p> <p>Objectives: Influence political decisions by providing technical data coming from project assessment</p> <p>Value proposition:</p> <p>Advantages: Can help to push the decisions</p> <p>Main use: at local/regional/national/EU level</p> <p>Alternative uses:</p> <p>What is new: results coming from WP2 are highly valuable and should help to foster even more the positive answer from policy makers</p> <p>Why is important: Being a coordination and innovation action, the most important is to create a change on the stakeholders perspective</p> <p>What needs does it meet: Agreement among partners on the scope and the means</p>
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	<p>CIC, EBA, ACR+ & CETENMA</p> <p>The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.</p>

Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Policymakers
Potential Customers	Policy makers and Public Authorities
Barriers	Disagreement among partners regarding the message.
Mitigation Measures	Dialogue among partners.

10.1.3. EBA

EBA has identified three (3) potential results that intends to exploit after the end of the project. Below these results are presented, along with the input that the partner provided.

10.1.3.1. RESULT NUMBER 1: GUIDELINES FOR FERTILISER PRODUCERS

Guidelines for fertiliser producers

Declared by	EBA
Type of Exploitable Result	Guidelines and recommendations
Title, Short Description and Main Features	Compilation of key non-technical, technical, market and regulatory information related to the manufacture of alternative fertilisers. The EBA will use this result to promote within its network the production of alternative fertilisers.
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None

IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	FER-PLAY Consortium
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	None
Potential Customers	Industry and producers of fertilisers
Barriers	Traditional value chains that are less keen to innovate
Mitigation Measures	Meetings with fertiliser producers

10.1.3.2. RESULT NUMBER 2: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PUBLIC ADMINISTRATIONS

Recommendations for public administrations

Declared by	EBA
Type of Exploitable Result	Guidelines and recommendations
Title, Short Description and Main Features	Practical suggestions in the form of policy briefs to help policy makers to deliver successful strategies and instruments for the market deployment of alternative fertilisers. The EBA will use this result to support our advocacy at the EU level.
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None

IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	FER-PLAY Consortium
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	None
Potential Customers	Policy makers and Public Authorities
Barriers	Traditional value chains that are less keen to innovate
Mitigation Measures	Meetings with policy makers

10.1.3.3. RESULT NUMBER 3: MULTI-ASSESSMENT OF IMPACTS, TRADE-OFFS AND FRAMEWORK CONDITIONS

Multi-assessment of impacts, trade-offs and framework conditions

Declared by	EBA
Type of Exploitable Result	Skills and know-how
Title, Short Description and Main Features	Conclusions of the LCSAs and technical + regulatory analysis of the selected alternative fertiliser value chains. The EBA will use this result to support our advocacy at the EU level.
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None

IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	FER-PLAY Consortium
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	None
Potential Customers	Industry
Barriers	Not identified
Mitigation Measures	Not identified

10.1.4. NURESYS

NURESYS has identified one (1) potential result that intends to exploit after the end of the project. Below this result is presented, along with the input that the partner provided.

10.1.4.1. RESULT NUMBER 1: INDUSTRIALISATION POTENTIAL OF ALTERNATIVE FERTILISERS

Industrialisation potential of alternative fertilisers

Declared by	NuReSys
Type of Exploitable Result	Skills and know-how
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Industrialization potential of alternative fertilisers</p> <p>Short Description: Results of the benchmark study of alternative fertilisers and their application technologies with existing fertilisers.</p> <p>Main features: Intensive research and comparison of the existing fertiliser</p>

application methodologies and costs for effective conventional fertiliser replacement.

Objectives: Quantitative & qualitative analysis of the potential application of alternative fertilisers.

Value proposition: Provides valuable insight of the potential 'market pull' for alternative fertilisers.

Advantages: Promoted use of alternative fertilisers.

Main use: Market introduction of alternative fertilisers. Guidelines for fertiliser application. Exploitation of possible ways of use for the fertiliser.

Alternative uses: Information can be used for legal guidelines and temporary subsidies to promote the use of these fertilisers.

What is new: The approach is on multiscale and has a wide scope (from recovery stage to ready to use fertiliser).

Why is important: It reflects the feasibility of application of these alternative fertilisers.

What needs does it meet: For an alternative fertiliser to be used, it needs: a useful morphology, a satisfactory nutrient content, a competitive cost and a positive (or neutral) environmental footprint.

This study will benchmark these needs compared to a conventional fertiliser.

Type of Exploitation	Commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	NuReSys, CIC & Cetaqua
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Agricultural Sector and Farmers
Potential Customers	Private Sector Farmers as 'end users' will be the most interested in these results as it will reflect the practicality for application of these fertilisers compared to the conventional.
Barriers	Incompatibility between parts of system

There might be cases where the alternative fertiliser is not compatible for application under the existing machinery or methodology. There might be a possibility that the alternative fertiliser on its own is insufficient to replace a conventional fertiliser.

Mitigation Measures

Further research into morphology of the product for ease of application. Product processing to suit the existing machinery. Further research in combination of various alternative fertilisers to make one complete fertiliser.

10.1.5. INAGRO

INAGRO has identified three (3) potential results that intends to exploit after the end of the project. Below these results are presented, along with the input that the partner provided.

10.1.5.1. RESULT NUMBER 1: DATABASE

Database

Declared by	Inargo
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Type of Exploitable Result	Data
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Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Database</p> <p>Short Description: The database was developed for Milestone 1. It is a public deliverable available online. It gathers all the info and knowledge the consortium could find on the value chains identified.</p> <p>Main features: https://fer-play.eu/resources/</p> <p>Objectives: Centralizing data that can be used and disseminated.</p> <p>Value proposition: It can be valuable for users to find all data and info centralised and to look for relevant products for their company/business.</p> <p>Advantages: User friendly</p> <p>Main use: Centralised data on alternative fertilisers where interested parties can retrieve info</p> <p>Alternative uses: It can be used to promote the FER-PLAY project.</p> <p>What is new: Centralization of data that is otherwise scattered.</p> <p>Why is important: Centralization of data that is otherwise scattered.</p> <p>What needs does it meet: Centralization of data that is otherwise scattered</p>
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Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	Inargo
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	None
Potential Customers	Researchers looking for information and data, policy makers looking for data, fertiliser industry to look at future options
Barriers	Inadequate financing It is a database that will need to be kept updated. After the end of the project, this will require additional funding and manpower.
Mitigation Measures	Participation in follow-up projects

10.1.5.2. RESULT NUMBER 2: KNOWLEDGE

Knowledge

Declared by	Inargo
Type of Exploitable Result	Skills and know-how

Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Gained knowledge, skills and know-how</p> <p>Short Description: New knowledge gained from the project can be used in the future for follow-up projects or other activities.</p> <p>Main features: Knowledge</p> <p>Objectives: Further development of skills and know-how</p> <p>Value proposition: It could be valuable for bringing in future project grants.</p> <p>Advantages: individual knowledge growth</p> <p>Main use: Knowledge to take into future work</p> <p>What is new: Some insights and know-how</p> <p>Why is important: To keep up with the latest developments</p> <p>What needs does it meet: Personal and organisational skill development</p>
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	<p>FER-PLAY Consortium</p> <p>The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.</p>
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	None
Potential Customers	<p>Knowledge could be shared with everyone. But at Inagro this will mostly be for farmers, researchers, the (alternative fertiliser) industry and policy makers.</p>
Barriers	<p>Regulation that hinders innovation</p> <p>The results can be ever so positive, if regulation does not allow the use of alternative fertilisers instead of mineral fertiliser and not animal manure, there is no room to use them in Flanders/the Netherlands.</p>
Mitigation Measures	Inclusion in the FPR and also the RENURE legislation.

10.1.5.3. RESULT NUMBER 3: GUIDELINES AND ADVICE

Guidelines and Advice	
Declared by	Inargo
Type of Exploitable Result	Guidelines and Recommendations
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Learned guidelines and recommendations</p> <p>Short Description: New guidelines and recommendations from the project can be used in the future in daily work.</p> <p>Main features: Learnt guidelines and recommendations</p> <p>Objectives: Development of advice</p> <p>Value proposition: Valuable in day-to-day advice</p> <p>Advantages: Developed advice for stakeholders</p> <p>Main use: Use in advice for stakeholders</p> <p>Alternative uses: In future projects</p> <p>What is new: Developed with the latest new insights</p> <p>Why is important: Developed with the latest new insights</p> <p>What needs does it meet: Advice development</p>
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	<p>FER-PLAY Consortium</p> <p>The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.</p>
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	None

Potential Customers	The ones Inagro would use most will be guidelines and recommendations for farmers. However, this could also be shared with other researchers, the (alternative fertiliser) industry and policy makers.
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Barriers	Regulation that hinders innovation The results can be ever so positive, if regulation does not allow the use of alternative fertilisers instead of mineral fertiliser and not animal manure, there is no room to use them in Flanders/the Netherlands.
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Mitigation Measures	Inclusion in the FPR and also the RENURE legislation.
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10.1.6. CETAQUA

CETAQUA has identified three (3) potential results that intends to exploit after the end of the project. Below these results are presented, along with the input that the partner provided.

10.1.6.1. RESULT NUMBER 1: ALTERNATIVE FERTILISERS DATABASE

Alternative fertilisers database

Declared by	Cetaqua
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Type of Exploitable Result	Data
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Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Alternative fertilisers database</p> <p>Short Description: The result of the project "Comprehensive overview on alternative fertiliser value chain" is a database gathering all the information submitted by the partners regarding the different value chains studied. It covers all phases of alternative's fertiliser life cycle: production, distribution/trade, storage and application on lands, diffusion into different environment. This database will be used as background information for further research, and future projects</p>
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Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
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Background IP	Yes
	A system suitable for the recovery of phosphorus from organic waste, such as activated sludge from a sewage treatment plant, and comprising solubilizing phosphorus contained in micro-organisms in the organic waste and precipitating it by stepwise crystallization (Brushite to precipitate calcium; Struvite in the absence or lack of Ca ²⁺), thus obtaining a Ca ²⁺ and phosphorus depleted stream specially suited for the application of nitrogen recovery methods (ion exchange techniques and membrane contactors).
IPR related to Background IP	Patent
Ownership of Result	FER-PLAY Consortium
	The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	None
Potential Customers	Researchers
Barriers	No barriers identified
Mitigation Measures	No measures identified

10.1.6.2. RESULT NUMBER 2: ALTERNATIVE FERTILISER SELECTION METHODOLOGY

Alternative fertiliser selection methodology

Declared by Cetaqua

Type of Exploitable Result	Methods
Title, Short Description and Main Features	The result of the project "Methodology for the selection of alternative fertilisers" is a methodology that allows the selection and classification of alternative fertilisers based on various relevant aspects (nutrient content, toxicity, TRL, etc.). The methodology is divided into two stages. A first stage, the funnelling process, based on a GO/NO GO approach that allows selection by six criteria, which facilitates the quick disposal of those fertilisers that do not meet the minimum requirements. In the second selection stage, the value chains that have received a GO were subjected to a scoring system. This stage allows a classification of fertilisers by score. This methodology developed within the framework of the project could be easily adapted to other applications. For CETAQUA, as a technology centre, it could be a tool to find out which fertilisers have the greatest potential for use in order to invest research resources in their recovery. As an alternative use, it could be extrapolated to decide which alternative fertilisers to apply in a certain region. To the best of our knowledge, we are not aware of a similar methodology that allows select and classify alternative fertilisers. This would allow comparison of different fertilisers quickly and easily based on all the different relevant aspects of a fertiliser.
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	All partners involved in WP1 The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	None
Potential Customers	Researchers
Barriers	No barriers identified

Mitigation Measures

No measures identified

10.1.6.3. RESULT NUMBER 3: RESULTS OF MULTIASSESSMENT

Results of multiassessment

Declared by	Cetaqua
Type of Exploitable Result	Skills and know-how
Title, Short Description and Main Features	The selected value chains will be submitted to a rigorous and holistic assessment to determine their environmental, social, economic impacts & trade-offs (via LCSA) as well as their technical and regulatory aspects. The assessment will be done in a way that allows the comparison not only with conventional fertiliser but between the selected value chain. To our knowledge there is little to none published studies with this comprehensive approach.
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	All partners involve in WP2 The co-ownership will be regulated according to the Article 14 of the GA.
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	None
Potential Customers	Researchers and Policy makers

Researchers will be able to take these results and continue to analyze more alternative fertilisers. Policy makers can obtain information on the environmental performance of certain fertilisers to inform possible changes in legislation.

Barriers	No barriers identified
Mitigation Measures	No measures identified

10.1.7. DRAXIS

DRAXIS has identified one potential result that intends to exploit after the end of the project. Below this result is presented, along with the input that the partner provided.

10.1.7.1. RESULT NUMBER 1: LCA SERVICES

LCA Services	
Declared by	Draxis
Type of Exploitable Result	Consulting Services
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: LCA consulting services</p> <p>Short Description: Provision of LCA consulting services to third parties to various parties, such as individual entrepreneurs, industrial sector, support in R&D actions of universities or European and National funded projects.</p> <p>Main features: Expand the knowledge base for conducting LCA analysis in the field of alternative fertilisers.</p> <p>Objectives: Expanding the client base to an additional target audience of the market.</p> <p>Value proposition: Bring forth state-of-the-art scientific knowledge to meet the needs of an expanding market.</p> <p>Advantages: State-of-the-art scientific knowledge and stakeholder involvement</p> <p>Main use: Provision of services.</p> <p>What is new: State-of-the-art scientific knowledge and stakeholder involvement.</p> <p>Why is important: Because LCA has become a necessary tool to estimate environmental impact and environmental performance.</p>

	What needs does it meet: Quantitative and standardized environmental assessment.
Type of Exploitation	Commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	Draxis
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Environmental Consulting Services
Potential Customers	Public Sector, Private Sector, Researchers, Public Authorities The provision of LCA can be useful for many sectors, since its popularity and importance is increasing and it is required, in many cases, by national or European legislation.
Barriers	Traditional value chains that are less keen to innovate Lack of awareness regarding the advantages that LCA can provide to producers of fertilisers.
Mitigation Measures	Participation in meeting with the relevant stakeholders in order to inform them regarding the results of the implementation of the LCA.

10.1.8. REVOLVE

REVOLVE has not identified an exploitable result that wishes to exploit after the end of the project.

10.1.9. ACR+

ACR+ has identified one (1) potential result that intends to exploit after the end of the project. Below this result is presented, along with the input that the partner provided.

10.1.9.1. RESULT NUMBER 1: GUIDELINES FOR LOCAL AND REGIONAL AUTHORITIES

Guidelines for local and regional authorities

Declared by	ACR+
Type of Exploitable Result	Guidelines and recommendations
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Practical suggestions to help policy makers deliver successful strategies and instruments for the market deployment of alternative fertilisers</p> <p>Short Description:</p> <p>Main features: Several (potentially) policy briefs written by ACR+ and EBA</p> <p>Objectives: To provide information to policy makers so that they can develop strategies and instruments to deploy the market of alternative fertilisers (EU-wide)</p> <p>Value proposition: The use of alternative fertilisers has positive impacts on the environment and allow EU MS to not depend on products (e.g., phosphorous collected outside-EU)</p> <p>Advantages:</p> <p>Main use: For policy makers (Eu-/national-/regional-level) to draft laws/recommendations to remove barriers to the development of the alternative fertiliser market</p> <p>Alternative uses: To promote the development of small companies/organizations developing alternative fertiliser value chains</p> <p>What is new:</p> <p>Why is important: This policy brief will be based on real experience gathered from conversations with local authorities and public administrations</p> <p>What needs does it meet: Anonymity of the sources (local authorities and public administrations)</p>
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None

IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	ACR+ & EBA
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Local and regional authorities, public administrations
Potential Customers	Policy Makers
Barriers	<p>Traditional value chains that are less keen to innovate</p> <p>The main barriers should be identified over the course of the project. Barriers might be different across Europe and possibly linked with the regulation, the habits of end-users regarding fertilising practices, the quality of local alternative fertilisers, the lack of trust of end-users, and the lack of connection regarding the governance of waste/wastewater activities and agriculture.</p>
Mitigation Measures	Strong political support to help develop alternative fertiliser producers.

10.1.10. COLDIRETTI

COLDIRETTI is not going to produce specific results as per effect of its involvement in the FER-PLAY project. They have a specific interest in promoting, among the selected chains, the one derived from digestate, those produced from the livestock sector, but we are not producing any specific result.

10.1.11. NATURLAND

NATURLAND has identified one (1) potential result that intends to exploit after the end of the project. Below this result is presented, along with the input that the partner provided.

10.1.11.1. RESULT NUMBER 1: IMPROVED KNOWLEDGE, NETWORKS

Improved knowledge, networks

Declared by	Naturland
Type of Exploitable Result	Guidelines and recommendations
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: Improved knowledge</p> <p>Short Description:</p> <p>Main features: Knowledge about alternative fertilisers</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <p>Value proposition:</p> <p>Advantages: More farmers use alternative fertilisers</p> <p>Main use: Selection of "best" fertilisers</p> <p>Alternative uses:</p> <p>What is new: Struvit is new, some of the other fertilisers are not new</p> <p>Why is important:</p> <p>What needs does it meet:</p>
Type of Exploitation	Non-commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None
Ownership of Result	None
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Farmers, advisers, environmental NGOs, politicians
Potential Customers	<p>Private Sector</p> <p>Many organic farmers have negative nutrient balances, especially P fertilisers are needed</p>

Barriers	Regulation that hinders innovation New interesting fertilisers are not listed in EU organic standards
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Mitigation Measures	Meetings with policy makers with the support of the network
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10.1.12. ASAJA

ASAJA has identified one (1) potential result that intends to exploit after the end of the project. Below this result is presented, along with the input that the partner provided.

10.1.12.1. RESULT NUMBER 1: NEW FERTILISERS

New Fertilizers

Declared by	ASAJA
Type of Exploitable Result	Product
Title, Short Description and Main Features	<p>Title: new fertilisers Short Description: use of now fertilisers Main features: alternative to traditional fertilization Objectives: awareness and promotion of the use Value proposition: waste valuation Advantages: low impact, new product Main use: agriculture Alternative uses: chemical and pharmaceutical industry What is new: origin of the fertiliser Why is important: reduce negative impact of fertilisers What needs does it meet: fertilization</p>
Type of Exploitation	Commercial
Background IP	None
IPR related to Background IP	None

Ownership of Result	Not identified
Protection of Result	None
Potential Market	Agricultural Sector
Potential Customers	Farmers
Barriers	Mismatch between market needs and the solution There is no market development, there is interest, but the production of these fertilisers is insufficient to cover the needs of the sectors
Mitigation Measures	Development of industry and training of producers for its use

